

The logo for Climateurope2 features the text "Climateurope2" in a white, serif font, centered on a rectangular background with a horizontal gradient from blue on the left to yellow on the right.

Climateurope2

Beta version of Climateurope2 platform operational

Deliverable 7.3

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate-neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this by providing climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and need for climate information has seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. Various activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

This Deliverable describes the approach towards and current status of the Beta version of the Climateurope2 platform, which has been distributed to a selected user board within the CE2 project to gather feedback that will be implemented in the next version of the platform. Working towards the final stable version of the platform in M36, there will be additional releases in between, but then feedback will be included from external user groups as well. The Beta version of the platform is shown via screenshots using three user flows that have different levels of user rights (public user, CE2 community basic and CE2 community approved).

The main sections of the platform are *co-create*, *explore* and *network*, which allows registered users (with sufficient rights) to publish and discuss drafts of guidelines and good practices until a consensus is reached and they are ready for public access (*co-create*). Publicly, it facilitates access to the final versions of documents via an interactive and user-friendly repository (*explore*). And finally, the “network” section hosts information in a catalogue about members in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network.

Keywords

Climateurope2, platform, climate services, best practices, guidelines, co-create, explore, network.

1 Functionalities Climateurope2 platform

1.1 General introduction

The Climateurope2 (CE2) platform supports internal discussions and engages the climate services community by making guidelines, good practices and recommendations regarding climate services widely available, easy to find and usable during and after the project's lifetime. Once fully developed, the platform will be accessible from the Climateurope2 website. In a secure environment, it allows registered users (with sufficient rights) to publish and discuss drafts of guidelines and good practices until a consensus is reached and they are ready for public access. Publicly, it facilitates access to the final versions of documents via an interactive and user-friendly repository. This is not to be confused with the 'project resource repository' that is for internal use only.

The web application back-end allows the Climateurope2 members to enter the guidelines and practices document with standardised metadata (title, tags, etc). In the front-end, the applications use that metadata to provide faceted search, automated classification and visualisation services to explore content resources and (using WebLizard technology) a *CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard* to oversee the content collection process, assess the quality of the extracted metadata and perform searches that further enrich the application. The platform is aimed at involving specialised audiences and stakeholders, but at the same time it will be one of the project outputs and a collection of materials for wider communication.

1.1.1 Main objective

The main objectives of the Climateurope2 platform are:

- To provide an interactive and user-friendly repository that provides easy access to good practices, recommendations and standardisation processes of climate services, and encourages community engagement and knowledge co-production.
- To connect and create a community (to incentivise people using the platform)
- The platform should also have a clear and intuitive navigation structure, making it easy for users to find the information that they need.

1.1.2 Design process

The functional and technical requirements have been gathered during an iterative stakeholders and project partners consultation, documented in Milestone 29 "Technical and functional specification for the Climateurope2 platform". Interviews were performed with potential users from the Climateurope2 consortium, with different roles and backgrounds, from which the main insights were extracted, and an affinity map was made to visualise the main insights and patterns found in the different interviews. Personas were defined based on actual research and extracted from the user interviews and observation data of real users. Scenarios were developed to explore and explain motivations for certain user needs and behaviours. These steps have ultimately resulted in a high-fidelity prototype of the platform (static-clickable) that marked the start of the platform development. This is made available as Milestone 30, handed over to the development team in WP7. We refer to more details on the designs and functions in those documents, they will not be repeated here.

1.1.3 Technical implementation

The development process of the platform follows a step-wise approach using the high-fidelity prototype as a basis. Several releases are foreseen after this Beta version, for which there will be contact with user group representatives to collect feedback. This Beta version of the platform has

been distributed to a selected user board within the CE2 project to gather feedback that will be implemented in the next version of the platform. Working towards the final stable version of the platform in M36, there will be additional releases in between, but then also feedback will be included from external user groups as well. The final version will have a restful Application Programming Interface (API) for future integration in other platforms such as Climate-ADAPT.

The platform is a custom-developed web application using Symfony PHP, including a database for user management behind the platform, a database for metadata best practices and a front-end input form open to (co)authors to place their publications. These publications will include the good practices that are extracted from project Deliverables by the experts. The practices can include different parts of a climate service workflow, e.g. from raw data to a data product. Each good practice publication follows a metadata template and receives its own persistent DOI/URI, which is findable using a repository with a search entry, enabled by using keywords. Visual analytics capabilities developed by partner WebLizard are embedded into the platform to provide aggregate representations of search results, to identify stakeholders and opinion leaders, and to assess the impact of events and communication activities. The visual analytics capabilities are available as widgets embedded into the platform and as a stand-alone CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard to provide more advanced analytic features to explore and navigate climate service-related content assets.

1.1.4 Navigation structure

The main sections of the platform are co-create, explore and network:

Co-create

The “co-create” section allows for collaboration in real-time on document consultation with multiple users and includes version control and commenting tools. The section is available for a selection of users (see 1.1.5 User rights) and facilitates interaction in the final stages of a document. The agreed approach is that collaborators first work together on their document in the internal project repository (Teedy) or other collaborative environments before publishing a mature draft version in the co-create section. This mature draft version can then be viewed here by relevant collaborators (chosen by the (co)author) that can provide feedback with comments under the document. Based on the received feedback, the mature draft version can then be revised and re-uploaded, which can be an iterative approach and repeated as many times as required. Once the final revision has taken place and the document is approved by all collaborators and (co)authors, it can be published and will be available publicly in the “explore” section.

Explore

The “explore” section is the main section of the Climateurope2 platform that contains the published documents (from the “co-create” section) related to climate services, developed by the Climateurope2 project but also the wider community. This section is open for all users without having to register (see 1.1.5 User rights). Documents can contain information on access guidelines, good practices, use cases, and other relevant materials through an easy-to-use catalogue.

There is also an embedded “LITE” version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard available in the “explore” section to enable users to browse CE2 content as well as the wider context on what is being published on climate services across regions and channels (news, companies, public sector, etc.). In addition to the embedded version, which is geared towards casual users and the public, a registered user gets access to the standalone PRO version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard.

Network

The “network” section hosts information in a catalogue about members in the network to identify connections and flow of information among actors in the network. It also facilitates interaction among

members, by introducing a chatting functionality. This section is only accessible for registered users (see 1.1.5 User rights).

1.1.5 User rights

The platform supports different users, and has three different levels of User Rights, allowing for placing access restrictions on different parts of the platform.

Public user

This user is not logged in, but can access published documents in the “explore” section and read related comments. This user gets access to the “LITE” version of the CE2 Visual Analytics dashboard, and a selected set of content sources to be determined by CE2 partners.

CE2 community basic

This user is registered via the platform and gets access to the same features as the public user. Additionally, this user gets access to the “network” section and the “professional” version of the CE2 dashboard, with more advanced analytic capabilities and additional content sources. He/she can place comments on published documents and can request to become CE2 community “approved” member, which grants access to the “co-create” section.

CE2 community approved

This user is part of the Climateurope2 project or an approved CE2 community member and has the same rights as the CE2 community user. Additionally, this user can log in using their Teedy credentials, which are also used to enter the internal project repository. This user gets access to the “co-create” section and can comment on the documents that they brought in as an author or where they are included as collaborators.

2 User flows

This chapter showcases the Climateurope2 platform, using the perspective from the three different user groups listed above.

The Climateurope2 platform Beta is available on the URL: <https://ce2-platform-beta.maris.nl/>

2.1 Public user

1. The user can explore the homepage to get familiar with the platform's features and options. Here, the main sections, co-create, explore and network are clearly visible and shortly explained. The "co-create" and "network" sections are not open to the public user. If the user does not have an account yet, when clicking on the "network" section, the user is asked to register. When clicking on the "co-create" section, the user is first asked to register and then request approval to become a CE2 community-approved member.

Figure 1. Homepage

- The user can navigate to the “explore” section, where the user can access the embedded LITE version of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard (the screenshot below shows the regional distribution of climate service-related online publications from companies (blue), the public sector (brown), non-profit organisations (green), news (yellow) as well as universities and research centres (orange)).

Figure 2. Visual Analytics Dashboard embedded

3. Within the “explore” section, the user is able to navigate to the “documents listing” page, where all the published documents can be found.

Figure 3. Documents listing page

4. On the “documents” page, the user can search for the relevant document, using the search bar or filters for the list of resources available. Once the document is found, it can be opened to obtain more information and display the abstract and furthermore, the document can be downloaded, and eventually a persistent URL to the document can be shared.

Figure 4. Document abstract

- Finally, the user is able to **read** comments placed under the documents by registered users. A comment can only be **placed** once the user is registered and logged in.

Figure 5. Comments under documents

2.2 CE2 community basic

In addition to the rights of the public user, the CE2 community basic member by registering has unlocked additional features that are showcased below. If this member wants to access the “co-create” page, he/she can now also request to become a CE2 community “approved” member. This also involves filling in more personal details and motivation/expertise as a 2nd step in registration.

- If not registered yet, the user can create a new account by clicking on ‘Sign up’ and providing the required information.

Figure 6. Sign up page

- The registered member is able to place comments on published documents.

Figure 7. Placing a comment on a published document

- In addition to the embedded version of the “explore” section, which is geared towards casual users and the public, the member gets access to the standalone PRO version of the *CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard*, available at climateurope2.weblyzard.com. It replaces the more linear responsive design approach of the embedded version with a synchronised display of multiple widgets that show extracted metadata along multiple context dimensions (time, region, topic classifications, etc.). The screenshot below segments climate services coverage by source, plots recent trends, clusters documents into “stories”, and provides advanced tooltips, additional background information and rapid-drill down operations (in this case, a click on the tag cloud term “risk analysis” shows why this keyword has been chosen as one of the top associations).

Figure 8. Visual Analytics Dashboard standalone PRO version

- This member can also access the “network” page. In this example, the input fields are still quite empty, as in this test version people have not provided all personal details.

Climateurope2 My Profile

Search documents by type, author, name About Actions Contact

> Network

Network

Develop the European climate service network to improve connection and engagement, encouraging open exchange of knowledge and data. Improve synergies between regional, national, European, and international activities and gain insights into the climate service community's needs for support and promotion.

Filter	Name	Research Line	Organisation	Role	Country	Contact
Author		Computer Science		Software developer	VA	Send Message
Research		Hydraulic Engineering		Project Engineer	NL	Send Message
					NL	Send Message
						Send Message
						Send Message
						Send Message
		Climate Services & Wildfire		Senior Climate Scientist	GB	Send Message
						Send Message
						Send Message
						Send Message

< 1/2 >

Figure 9. Network page

2.3 CE2 community approved

In addition to the rights of the CE2 community basic member, the CE2 community approved member has unlocked additional features that are showcased below. This user is either an approved CE2 community basic member (via the request form), or part of the CE2 community (project member) that automatically unlocks this status.

1. This member is able to access the “co-creation” section, where users can collaborate and work together on projects and documents. Documents where the member is not included as (co)author or collaborator, will not show up on the “co-create” page.

Climateurope2 My Profile

Search documents by type, author, name

About Actions Contact

Co-create

Co-creation

Trigger focused discussions with the wider expert community on climate services and the standardisation of their components. This will be done through the sharing of early versions of project documents, allowing registered users to collaborate and enable the co-production of knowledge, aligning with open science practices, thus accelerating the consensus process.

Create a new document

Filter	
Component	
Type	
Status	
Priority	
Author	
Spatial domain	
Sort by	

- INNOVA Ezine - Challenges and Solutions for Urban Water Supply in a Changing Climate and World
2023-12-04 [Best Practices](#) [Policy context & support](#)
- Temperature projections Mediterranean
2023-11-30 [Best Practices](#) [Data & Data process](#)
- Climate velocity projections for the North Sea
2023-11-30 [Best Practices](#) [Data & Data process](#)

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Figure 10. Co-create page

- The member can upload the work-in-progress document by clicking on the “Upload” button and selecting a file from the computer. The member should complete the required information, such as the document’s title, description, tags, and collaborators. If the member is listed as (co)author, he/she is able to include others as (co)author or collaborator.

Climateurope2 My Profile

Search documents by type, author, name About Actions Contact

Home > Co-create > New document

New document

With just a few easy clicks, you can begin a journey of teamwork, sharing your document with other colleagues.

Let's start:

- 1 Fill the information required
- 2 Start collaboration
- 3 Collect feedback
- 4 Publish

Document information

Title:

Author:

Abstract:

Component:

Topic:

Special Domain:

Team information

Collaborators:

Document privacy: Private Open to all

Private:

Status:

Upload attachment

Climate V...th Sea.pdf

Upload your document by dragging and dropping it here, or click to browse and select a file from your device.

[Continue >](#)

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Figure 11. Form for creating a new document

- The member should check the document's status periodically to see if any feedback or comments have been added by other users and respond to any comments or feedback as needed. The member can use the platform's collaboration tools (e.g. chat, comments, annotations) to communicate with colleagues and make revisions. Once the (co)author has incorporated the feedback and made necessary revisions, a new version of the document can be uploaded via the form above. Comments on the draft documents can be placed by collaborators or (co)authors.

Figure 12. Comments under a collaborative document

- If the document is approved by the collaborators and (co)authors, it can be published, so that other members can see the final version.

Climateurope2 My Profile About Actions Contact

Search documents by type, author, name

[Home](#) > [Co-create](#) > Climate velocity projections for the north sea

1 Fill the information required 2 Start collaboration 3 Collect feedback 4 Publish

Document information

Title
Climate velocity projections for the North Sea

Authors
Tjerk Krijger

Abstract
Test

Component
Data & Data process

Type
Reports

Spatial Domain
European

Upload attachment

Current file: [Climate Velocity North Sea.pdf](#)

Upload your document by dragging and dropping it here, or click to browse and select a file from your device.

[Publish document](#)

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Figure 13. Publishing a document

5. The document is now made available for everyone to see in the “documents” section.

The screenshot shows the 'All Documents' page on the Climateurope2 platform. At the top, there is a search bar with the placeholder text 'Search documents by type, author, name'. To the right of the search bar are navigation links for 'About', 'Actions', and 'Contact', along with a 'My Profile' button. Below the search bar, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home > Explore > All Documents'. The main heading is 'See all documentation'. A paragraph below the heading states: 'Our document section is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest research and developments in climate services. Here, you can find a wide range of documents, including guidelines, vocabulary, reports, papers, and presentations, all of which are available for download.' Below this text is a list of documents. On the left, there is a filter sidebar with categories: 'Filter', 'Component', 'Type', 'Spatial domain', and 'Sort by'. The document list shows two entries: 1. 'INNOVA Ezine – Challenges and Solutions for Urban Water Supply in a Changing Climate and World' dated '2023-12-04', with tags 'Best Practices' and 'Policy context & support'. 2. 'Climate-velocity projections for the North Sea' dated '2023-11-30', with tags 'Best Practices' and 'Data & Data process'. At the bottom of the page, there is a blue footer containing the 'Funded by the European Union' logo, a disclaimer: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056933. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.', the 'Climateurope2' logo, copyright information '© 2024 All Rights Reserved', and links for 'Privacy Policy', 'Legal Notice', and 'Wiki'. Social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube are also present.

Figure 14. Published documents

3 Next steps

This Beta version of the platform has been distributed to a selected user board within the CE2 project to gather feedback. Based on this feedback, the most important planned modifications on the platform are listed below.

Planned modifications on the platform:

- Possible rework of the “co-create” steps, to make it more intuitive on how to collaborate on the documents.
- Possible rework of the home page to increase visibility of the “documents” page, by making the page accessible from the homepage.
- Incorporating additional feedback from test users into the LITE and Professional user interface versions of the CE2 Visual Analytics Dashboard (accessible via the “explore” page and via climateurope2.weblyzard.com, respectively). We plan to provide more content sources, including additional stakeholder websites and scientific publications, refine the available “bookmarks” (stored advanced searches that can be used by all or selected groups of users) and produce a video tutorial to guide first-time users through the process of exploring content assets.
- Updating the user profile information fields, based on gathered feedback.
- Other modifications based on gathered feedback, e.g. filters, bugs, user experience, buttons.

After the planned modifications are incorporated, a webinar will be set-up where the platform will be demonstrated. Here, feedback will be gathered and the most prominent ones will be implemented in the new version of the platform. This new version of the platform aims to be operational, such that the members can start filling it with content. Working towards the final stable version of the platform in M36 (if possible, an earlier public release is foreseen to support the dissemination and impact of the project), there will be additional releases in between, but then also feedback will be included from external user groups as well. The final version will come with a restful Application Programming Interface (API) for future integration in other platforms such as Climate-ADAPT.